

Effect of Position Analysis, Recruitment and Selection Employees on the Performance of the State Civil Apparatus in the Regional Secretariat of Bolaang Regency North Mongondow

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Abstract

This study aims to: (1) To determine the effect of: job analysis on ASN performance, recruitment on ASN performance, employee selection on ASN performance, (2) To determine the effect of job analysis, recruitment and employee selection together on ASN performance.

This research is research with a quantitative approach, the research will be pre-determined, statistical data analysis and statistical data interpretation.

Research Results: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis shows: $Y = 2,834 + 0,500X_1 + 0,542X_2 - 0,065 X_3$. F-count is 100,152 with a significance level of 0.000. And the value of F-table = $F(k;n-k) = F(3;48) = 2,798$. Because the probability is $0.000 < 0,05$ and the F-count $< F$ -table ($100,152 > 2,798$) thus the independent variables simultaneously or jointly affect the ASN Performance variable; Adjusted R Square = 0.865, meaning that only 86.50 percent of the variation in ASN performance (Y) can be explained by the independent variables. While the remaining 13.50% is explained by other reasons.

Suggestion: Analysis of Position, Recruitment, and Employee Selection have a positive influence on ASN Performance; thus, these three variables need to be maintained as a reference for ASN to move in to the Regional Secretariat; In order to improve the performance of ASN, it is necessary to pay attention to the implementation of a good Job Analysis, Recruitment and Selection of Employees; The placement of ASN in the Regional Secretariat should refer to the Position Analysis

Keywords: Position Analysis, Recruitment, Selection, ASN Performance

1. Introduction

Job analysis plays a very important role in employee placement. With the job analysis, it will produce employees who are able to work effectively and efficiently in achieving

organizational goals, so that they are in accordance with the needs of the organization both in terms of quality and quantity. To get productive employees, the main problem is placing each employee in a job and position that is in accordance with their talents, interests and abilities so that they can work fairly according to their abilities, expertise and/or skills and experience background. For this reason, the creation of a job analysis design is a demand for the organization. Through proper job analysis, all information regarding a position will be obtained, including the dimensions of work, duties, responsibilities, characteristics of human resources and working conditions.

With these dimensions, organizations can compile job descriptions that are truly in accordance with the characteristics of each position, so that the job analysis used can contribute to increasing employee performance productivity.

If the recruitment is based on needs according to job analysis and workload analysis, it will get a quality State Civil Apparatus and will ultimately have an impact on performance. In this research, the intended recruitment is to recruit existing State Civil Apparatus to be placed in the Regional Secretariat of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency.

The government has abandoned the conventional CPNS recruitment system pattern that has been used so far, BKN together with the PAN Ministry issued a CPNS selection pattern using the use of the Computer Assisted Test. CAT is a selection method using computer aids that can be used for CPNS recruitment tests (Martin, 2015).

The implementation of policies with this new system is expected in the selection process to be more transparent, accountable, objective, non-discriminatory and free from KKN, and also to obtain professional, honest and responsible employees. In this study, the intended employee selection is ASN who work outside the Regional Secretariat who are recruited and then selected to be defined. For those who do not pass the selection, they will find a placement according to their capacity and expertise

To encourage the performance and careers of the State Civil Apparatus in the future, the government through this management also encourages the improvement of the professionalism of positions, competencies and talent performance, as well as providing clarity and certainty of talent careers in the context of accelerating sustainable career development (Marliani, 2018).

Until now, the number of ASN in North Bolaang Mongondow Regency in 2020 is 2,449 people (870 men and 1,579 women). And the Regional Secretariat, the number of ASN in 2020 is 105 people. To improve the performance of the local government apparatus, they seek to provide Regional Performance Allowances for each civil servant. However, the performance of civil servants has not lived up to expectations. This can be seen from the still not optimal public services to get their rights in public services.

So far, the implementation of position analysis within the North Bolaang Mongondow regional government, especially the regional secretariat, has fulfilled the procedures and stages. This job analysis is useful because several indicators, one of which is educational qualifications, are considered in determining someone to occupy a certain position. Job analysis is also the most basic standard for determining a person's placement in a place.

The regional secretariat does need qualified employees so that recruitment is carried out from outside the regional secretariat. Recruitment means placing existing employees in positions. For the determination, there is a Baperjakat that considers based on certain criteria for a person to occupy a position. For the selection in order to fill the vacancies in the Regional Secretariat, there are still some that still need to be addressed because they are still not in accordance with the job analysis. For performance in general, it is still not quite satisfactory.

Understanding Administration

Administration based on etymology comes from Latin which consists of ad + ministrare, which operationally means to serve, assist and fulfill (Hadari, 2015). In the original language, the noun administration and the adjective administrative are formed. While in English it is administration and in Indonesian it is administration.

Etymologically or the origin of the word, administration comes from the English language administration, with the infinitive form to administer which is defined as to manage (Marliani, 2018). Administration also comes from Dutch administrative, which has the meaning of including administration, management of organizational activities, resource management.

Administration is the entire process of implementing the decisions that have been taken and the implementation is generally carried out by two or more human beings to achieve predetermined goals [12].

The term Public comes from English Public which means general, community or country. Public can also mean residents, communities, citizens, and the people. Sociologically, society is defined as a system of social relations between humans who live bound by mutually agreed norms or values. Meanwhile, the public is a collection of people who have the same concerns, interests, or interests and are not bound by certain values and norms.

Understanding Public Administration

Public administration has actually existed since time immemorial, it will arise in an organized society (Tanumihardjo et al., 2014). In the historical record of human civilization, in South Asia, including Indonesia, China, and Ancient Egypt, a system of governance arrangements was obtained. This arrangement system is now known as public / state administration.

Definition of Human Resources

The explanation of humans as resources shows that humans are unique and complex creatures, which in working in an organization/company environment must be treated with a good quality of work life in order to enable them to work effectively, efficiently, productively and with quality. In the form of providing opportunities to participate in developing their careers, being treated fairly in resolving the conflicts they face, being supervised honestly and objectively, getting decent wages (Mangkunegara, 2017).

Human resources are all the capabilities or potentials of the population residing in a certain area along with their demographic, social and economic characteristics or characteristics that can be utilized for development purposes. So discussing human resources

means discussing the population with all its potential or abilities. Human potential involves two aspects, namely aspects of quantity and quality. Demographic characteristics are quantitative aspects of human resources that can be used to describe the number and growth of the population, population distribution and population composition (Mangkunegara, 2017).

Job Analysis

Job analysis is a systematic way that is able to identify and analyze what requirements are needed in a job and the personnel needed in a job so that the selected human resources are able to carry out the job well.

From the results of the job analysis, the organization will be able to determine what characteristics a prospective employee must have before occupying a position, the outputs of which are job specifications and job descriptions. Job analysis as the basis for performance appraisal for employees. This performance appraisal is usually carried out once a year, however, it all comes back to the policies of an organization itself (Syafie, 2019). The results of the performance appraisal are used as the basis by a staffing agency for promotions and classes.

Recruitment

Recruitment is an effort to find and influence prospective workers to want to apply for job vacancies offered by a company (Hasibuan, 2019). Recruitment is a process of gathering a number of applicants who have the appropriate qualifications required by the company, to be employed in the company (Mathis & Jackson, 2012). Recruitment is a series of activities to find and attract job applicants with the motivation, abilities, skills and knowledge needed to cover the deficiencies identified in staffing planning.

Employee selection

Selection is a series of human resource management processes. After the company has forecast its human resource needs and determined the job requirements and job descriptions, local governments can continue the human resource management process. Selection is the process of selecting applicants to serve as state civil servants and placing them in positions required by the organization. In other words, Selection is a process of matching the needs and requirements of the organization to the skills and qualifications of job applicants. This selection process must adhere to the principle of "Right People in the Right Jobs", namely placing the right people in the right jobs (Garaika & Margahana, 2019).

The placement of Candidates for Civil Servants is carried out after being declared to have passed the selection and submitting administrative requirements and given the identity number of the prospective civil servants and placed according to the designated formation by taking into account their education and experience (Mangkunegara, 2017). Thus, the placement of each prospective civil servant is adjusted to the needs of the organization and should be based on the principle of "the right man in the right place".

Performance

Every work that is efficient is of course also effective, because in terms of the results, goals and desired consequences of the action have been achieved maximally. Performance is a reference to the level of success in achieving job requirements.

Performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him (Mangkunegara, 2017). Rismawati & Bachtiar in (Adha & Syarif, 2022) that the performance is an act or implementation of the task that the has completed within a certain period

Employee performance is the extent to which an employee achieves the work goals that have been set by the organization. It includes the tasks, responsibilities, and outcomes that are expected from a particular job position (Cardy & Leonard, in (Rachman et al., 2023).

State Civil Apparatus

State Civil Apparatus Employees, hereinafter referred to as ASN Employees, are civil servants and government employees with a work agreement who are appointed by the staffing officer and assigned tasks in a government position or assigned other state duties and are paid according to the laws and regulations (*Peraturan Pemerintah Republik Indonesia Nomor 11 Tentang Manajemen Pegawai Negeri Sipil*, 2017).

2. Methods

This research is research with a quantitative approach. Quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to examine certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical, with the aim of testing hypotheses. which has been established (Simamora, 2014).

This research was conducted in North Bolaang Mongondow Regency, for 2 (two) months, namely: October to December 2021.

The population in this study is ASN at the Regional Secretariat of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency, which until 2021 (October) amounted to 105 people.

This study uses a regression analysis technique using the multiple regression equation formula, namely: $Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3$ [11]

Description:

Y = ASN Performance; X_1 = Job Analysis; X_2 = Recruitment; X_3 = Employee selection;

$b_1 - b_3$ = regression coefficient to be interpreted; a = constant; e = error.

3. Results

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

From the results of the Multiple Linear Regression estimation using the SPSS for windows program, it can be concluded that the multiple linear regression equation in this study is as follows : $Y = 8.303 + 0.018X_1 + 0.432X_2 + 0.590X_3$;

Where:

Y = ASN Performance; X_1 = Position Analysis; X_2 = Recruitment; and X_3 = Employee selection

The multiple linear regression model mentioned above can be explained as follows:

- a) The constant value is 8.303, implying that when the variables job analysis (X_1), recruitment (X_2), and selection (X_3) remain constant and unchanged, the performance of ASN (Y) is expected to increase by 8.303 units. In other words, holding job analysis, recruitment, and selection constant, any change in the performance of ASN is associated with an increase of 8.303 units.
- b) Position Analysis (X_1) has a positive effect on ASN performance with a coefficient value of 0.018. This implies that for every increase of 0.018 units in job analysis (X_1), the performance of ASN is expected to increase by 0.018 units. Conversely, if there is a decrease of 0.018 units in job analysis, the ASN performance is anticipated to decrease by the same amount.
- c) Recruitment (X_2) has a positive effect on ASN performance, as indicated by a coefficient value of 0.432. This implies that for every increase of 0.432 units in recruitment (X_2), the performance of ASN is expected to increase by 0.432 units. Conversely, if there is a decrease of 0.432 units in recruitment, the ASN performance is anticipated to decrease by the same amount.
- d) Employee Selection (X_3) has a positive effect on ASN performance, indicated by a coefficient value of 0.590. This suggests that for every increase of 0.590 units in employee selection (X_3), the performance of ASN is expected to increase by 0.590 units. Conversely, if there is a decrease of 0.590 units in employee selection, the ASN performance is anticipated to decrease by the same amount.

T test (Individual/partial)

Based on the results of calculations with SPSS, it can be interpreted as follows:

- 1) Variable X_1 (job analysis), t -count = 7.246 and significance level = 0.000. Thus, because $7.246 > 1.678$ with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.050$, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that there is an effect of variable X_1 (job analysis) on variable Y (performance of ASN). The analysis results indicate that variable X_1 (job analysis) has a significant influence on variable Y (performance of civil servants). The t -value of 7.246 with a significance level of 0.000 suggests that the difference between the group undergoing job analysis and the other group is highly significant. By rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0) and accepting the alternative hypothesis (H_a), we can conclude that the presence of job analysis has a positive impact on the performance of civil servants.
- 2) Variable X_2 (recruitment), t -count = 2.294 and significance level = 0.000. Thus, because $2,294 > 1,678$ with a significance level of $0.026 < 0.05$, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that there is an effect of X_2 (recruitment) on the Y variable (ASN

performance). The analysis of Variable X2 (recruitment) reveals a t-value of 2.294, accompanied by a significance level of 0.000. With a t-value greater than the critical value of 1.678 and a significance level of 0.026, which is less than the conventional threshold of 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_a). This signifies a substantial impact of X2 (recruitment) on the Y variable (performance of civil servants). In other words, the results suggest that the recruitment process significantly influences the performance of ASN.

- 3) Variable X3 (employee selection), t-count = 2,987 and significance level = 0.154. Thus, because $2.987 > 1.678$ with a significance level of $0.004 < 0.05$, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that there is an effect of variable X3 (employee selection) on variable Y (performance of ASN). Variable X3 (employee selection) demonstrates a t-value of 2.987 with a significance level of 0.154. Given that 2.987 exceeds the critical value of 1.678 and the significance level of 0.004 is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted. Consequently, this indicates a significant effect of variable X3 (employee selection) on variable Y (performance of civil servants). In essence, the results suggest that the process of employee selection significantly influences the performance of ASN.

F Test (Simultaneous Test)

Based on the results of calculations with SPSS, it can be interpreted that in the ANOVA test or F-test, it can be obtained:

- 1) The calculated F value is 11,411 with a significance level of 0.025.
- 2) F-table value = $F(k;n-k) = F(3;48) = 2,798$.
- 3) The probability is less than 0.05 or $0.025 < 0.05$.
- 4) F-count $>$ F-table ($11,411 > 2,798$)

Because $0.000 < 0.05$ or $11.411 > 2.798$, there is an influence of independent variables which include Job Analysis (X1), Recruitment (X2), and Employee Selection (X3) simultaneously on the dependent variable. ASN Performance (Y). Since the significance level is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, or the F-statistic (11.411) is greater than the critical value (2.798), it can be concluded that there is a collective influence of the independent variables, namely Job Analysis (X1), Recruitment (X2), and Employee Selection (X3), on the dependent variable, ASN Performance (Y). This indicates that the combined impact of Job Analysis, Recruitment, and Employee Selection is statistically significant in explaining variations in ASN Performance.

Based on the SPSS Model Summary output, the Adjusted R Square is 0.865. This indicates that approximately 86.50 percent of the variability in ASN performance (Y) can be accounted for by the independent variables, which are job analysis (X1), recruitment (X2), and employee selection (X3). The remaining 13.50 percent ($100\% - 86.50\%$) of the variation is attributed to factors outside the scope of this study—other reasons or variables that were not specifically examined in the model.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 1. Tolerance Value and Variant Inflation Factor (VIF)

No	Variabel	Tolerance	VIF
1	X ₁ (Anjab)	0,609	1,641
2	X ₂ (Rekrutmen)	0,488	2,050
3	X ₃ (Seleksi)	0,552	1,813

Source: Research Results

From the data above, it can be seen that the tolerance value for each variable is > 0.10 and the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value is < 10 , which means that there is no multicollinearity problem or there is no multicollinearity between independent variables in the regression model.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Based on the conducted data processing, the results of the Heteroscedasticity test are as follows:

1. Job Analysis: Significance = 0.441 (> 0.05)
2. Recruitment: Significance = 0.068 (> 0.05)
3. Employee Selection: Significance = 0.107 (> 0.05)

The significance values for all three independent variables are greater than 0.05. This implies that there is no evidence of heteroscedasticity, as the data points exhibit a consistent spread above and below the 0 on the Y axis. In other words, the variance of the residuals remains constant across different levels of the independent variables, supporting the assumption of homoscedasticity in the regression model.

Normality test

Based on the data processing that has been done, the results of the Normality test can be seen that the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line, so the regression model of this study meets the assumption of normality. In Kolmogorov Smirnov's One Sample test, a significant value of 0.200 is obtained. Thus, the variables in this study are normal, where $0.200 > 0.05$. Upon analyzing the data, the results of the Normality test indicate that the data distribution follows the diagonal line, aligning with the direction of the diagonal. Consequently, it can be concluded that the regression model in this study satisfies the assumption of normality. In the Kolmogorov-Smirnov's One Sample test, a significant value of 0.200 is obtained. This result indicates that the variables under investigation in this study exhibit a normal distribution, given that the significance value (0.200) is greater than the conventional threshold of 0.05.

Linearity Test

Based on the results of data processing with SPSS, it can be seen that:

- a) independent variable X1 (job analysis) with dependent variable Y (performance of ASN), where deviation from linearity $> \alpha$ or $0.822 > 0.05$, and $F\text{-count} < F\text{-table}$ or $0.537 < 2.798$. The conclusion is that there is a linear relationship between the independent variable X1 (job analysis) and the dependent variable Y (ASN performance).
- b) independent variable X2 (recruitment) with dependent variable Y (ASN performance), where deviation from linearity $> \alpha$ or $0.738 > 0.05$, and $F\text{-count} < F\text{-table}$ or $0.422 < 2.798$. The conclusion is that there is a linear relationship between the independent variable X2 (recruitment) and the dependent variable Y (ASN performance).
- c) The independent variable X3 (employee selection) with the dependent variable Y (ASN performance), where deviation from linearity $> \alpha$ or $0.242 > 0.05$, and $F\text{-count} < F\text{-table}$ or $1.403 < 2.798$, the conclusion that there is a linear relationship between independent variable X3 (employee selection) with the dependent variable Y (performance of ASN).

4. Discussion

Interview result

Interviews were conducted in order to know for sure the process of recruitment and selection of employees assigned to the Regional Secretariat. This interview is also intended to strengthen the results of the research.

In general, the results obtained in the interview process with informants in the Organizational Section of the Regional Secretariat of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency as the person in charge of job analysis, recruitment, and selection of employees, the fact is that there are official placements that are not in accordance with the job analysis, which are as follows:

- 1) RAN, the person concerned has not fulfilled all the requirements in accordance with the Job Requirements in the Job Analysis, the elements that have not been fulfilled are: Course / Training - Levels, Course / Training - Job Technical.
- 2) HST, the person concerned has not fulfilled all the requirements in accordance with the Job Requirements in the Job Analysis, the elements that have not been fulfilled are: Course / Training - Technical.
- 3) YEK, the person concerned has not fulfilled all the requirements in accordance with the Position Requirements in the Job Analysis, the elements that have not been fulfilled are: Service Period and Rank Group.
- 4) GTO, the person concerned has not fulfilled all the requirements in accordance with the Job Requirements in the Job Analysis, the elements that have not been fulfilled are: Course / Training - Technical.
- 5) RKM, the person concerned has not fulfilled all the requirements in accordance with the Job Requirements in the Job Analysis, the elements that have not been fulfilled are: Work Experience.
- 6) HKU, the person concerned has not fulfilled all the requirements in accordance with the Job Requirements in the Job Analysis, the elements that have not been fulfilled are: Course / Training - Technical.

- 7) JAK, the person concerned has not fulfilled all the requirements in accordance with the Job Requirements in the Job Analysis, the elements that have not been fulfilled are: Course / Training - Technical and Work Experience.

Research Instrument Test

1) Validity Test

The validity test shows that the r-count of each variable is greater than the r-table (0.279) and the significance level of each variable is less than 0.05. The results of the tests that have been carried out are as follows:

Validation test of Job Analysis variable (X1)

In the job analysis variable (X1) there are 7 questions:

- (1) Question 1 (A1) r-count is 0.559,
- (2) Question 2 (A2) r-count is 0.454,
- (3) Question 3 (A3) r-count is 0.457,
- (4) Question 4 (A4) r-count is 0.471,
- (5) Question 5 (A5) r-count is 0.384.
- (6) Question 6 (A6) r-count is 0.518.
- (7) Question 7 (A7) r-count is 0.296.

When compared with the r-table of 0.279, the r-count value for each question is greater than the r-table value. Thus, it can be said that each question is valid.

b) Recruitment variable validation test (X2)

In the recruitment variable (X2) there are 3 questions:

- (1) Question 1 (R1) r-count is 0.434,
- (2) Question 2 (R2) r-count is 0.574,
- (3) Question 3 (R3) r-count is 0.520,

When compared with the r-table of 0.279, the r-count value for each question is greater than the r-table value. Thus, it can be said that each question is valid.

c) Validation test of Employee Selection variable (X3)

In employee selection (X3) there are 3 questions:

- (1) Question 1 (S1) r-count is 0.610,
- (2) Question 2 (S2) r-count is 0.687,
- (3) Question 3 (S3) r-count is 0.652,

When compared with the r-table of 0.279, the r-count value for each question is greater than the r-table value. Thus, it can be said that each question is valid.

d) ASN Performance variable validation test (Y)

In the performance of ASN (Y) there are 5 questions:

- (1) Question 1 (K1) r-count is 0.448,
- (2) Question 2 (K2) r-count is 0.641,
- (3) Question 3 (K3) r-count is 0.643,
- (4) Question 4 (K4) r-count is 0.543,
- (5) Question 5 (K5) r-count is 0.533.

When compared with the r-table of 0.279, the r-count value for each question is greater than the r-table value. Thus, it can be said that each question is valid.

2) Reliability Test

A variable is said to be reliable if it gives a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.60 [2]. If r-count $>$ r-table then the question is "reliable" and if r-count $<$ r-table then the question is "unreliable". Reliability test shows that the Cronbach Alpha value of each variable is greater than 0.60 meaning reliable according (Ghozali, 2016).

Thus, it means that the questionnaire which is an indicator of each variable is reliable or reliable. From the results of the tests that have been carried out as follows: job analysis variable (X1) Cronbach Alpha value of 0.697, recruitment variable (X2) Cronbach Alpha value of 0.647, employee selection variable (X3) Cronbach Alpha value of 0.952, and ASN performance variables (Y) the Cronbach Alpha value is 0.718.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

From the results of the Multiple Linear Regression estimation using the SPSS for windows program, the multiple linear regression equation in this study is as follows: $Y = 8.303 + 0.018X_1 + 0.432X_2 + 0.590X_3$. This equation can be explained as follows:

- 1) The increase in the Job Analysis variable (X1) will be followed by an increase in the ASN Performance variable (Y), if other variables that affect it are in a Ceteris Paribus state. This means that if the job analysis variable increases by 0.018 units, it will be followed by an increase in ASN performance by 0.018 units.
- 2) The increase in the Recruitment variable (X2) will be followed by an increase in the ASN Performance variable (Y), if other variables that affect it are in a Ceteris Paribus state. This means that if the recruitment variable increases by 0.432, it will be followed by an increase in ASN performance of 0.432.
- 3) The increase in the Employee Selection variable (X3) will not be followed by an increase in the ASN Performance variable (Y), if other variables that affect it are in a Ceteris Paribus state. This means that if the employee selection variable increases by 0.590, it will be followed by a decrease in ASN performance by 0.590.

- 4) Based on the resulting regression line, it can be seen that of the three variables used in this study the one that has the greatest influence on ASN performance is the employee selection variable of 0.590.

T-test (Individual/partial)

The results of the t-test showed the significance value of each variable were: job analysis (X1), a significance value of 0.000; recruitment (X2) a significance value of 0.026; and employee selection (X3) a significance value of 0.004. In the calculation results obtained t-count of: job analysis (X1) t-count value of 7.246; recruitment(X2) t-count value of 2.294; and employee selection (X3) the t-count value is 2.987, while the t-table value is 1.677.

Of the independent variables in this study, the dominant influence on the dependent variable is: job analysis (X1), this means: job analysis (X1) is the most important in determining the performance of ASN at the Regional Secretariat of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency.

F Test (Simultaneous Test)

From the results of the F test, it shows that the probability of the independent variable used in this study is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) and $F\text{-count} > F\text{-table}$ ($11,411 > 2,789$) so it can be stated that the independent variable which includes Job Analysis (X1), Recruitment (X2), and Employee Selection (X3) simultaneously or jointly affect the ASN Performance variable (Y).

Determinant Test (R²)

Then the results of the calculation of the Coefficient of Determination (R²), it can be concluded that the independent variables in this study: job analysis (X1), recruitment (X2), and employee selection (X3) are able to explain 86.50 percent of the variation in ASN performance (Y). While the remaining 13.50 is explained by other reasons outside the model that were not examined in this study.

Classic assumption test

1) Multicollinearity Test

The tolerance value for each variable is > 0.10 and the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value is < 10 , which means that there is no multicollinearity problem or there is no multicollinearity between independent variables in the regression model.

2) Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity test results show:

a) Job Analysis; Significance $0.441 > 0.05$

b) Recruitment;

Significance $0.068 > 0.05$

c) Employee Selection;

Significance $0.107 > 0.05$

The significance values of the three independent variables are all greater than 0.05, meaning that there is no heteroscedasticity, because the points spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis.

3) Normality Test

The results of the normality test show that the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line, so the regression model of this study fulfills the assumption of normality. In the Kolmogorov Smirnov One Sample test, a significant value of 0.200 was obtained. Thus, the variables in this study were normal, where $0.200 > 0.05$.

4) Linearity Test

The linearity test shows that:

- a) independent variable X1 (job analysis) with dependent variable Y (performance of ASN), where deviation from linearity $> \alpha$ or $0.822 > 0.05$, and F-count $< F$ -table or $0.537 < 2.798$. Thus, it can be concluded that there is a linear relationship between the independent variable X1 (job analysis) and the dependent variable Y (ASN performance).
- b) The independent variable X2 (recruitment) with the dependent variable Y (ASN performance), where deviation from linearity $> \alpha$ or $0.738 > 0.05$, and F-count $< F$ -table or $0.422 < 2.798$. Thus, it is concluded that there is a linear relationship between the independent variable X2 (recruitment) and the dependent variable Y (the performance of ASN).
- c) The independent variable X3 (employee selection) with the dependent variable Y (ASN performance), where deviation from linearity $> \alpha$ or $0.242 > 0.05$, and F-count $< F$ -table or $1.403 < 2.798$, thus the conclusion that there is there is a linear relationship between the independent variable X3 (employee selection) and the dependent variable Y (the performance of ASN)

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The results of surveys conducted in order to link the results of previous observations; it was found that there were several ASN whose placements were not in accordance with the job analysis on the grounds that the number of employees was still limited. There are employees who are recruited without going through the actual process. And similarly with employee selection, there are those who do not go through the proper process even though the procedures and stages already exist. All this because of the needs of the organization, and through good judgment.

2. Analysis of the effect of job analysis, recruitment, and selection of employees on the performance of ASN at the Regional Secretariat of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency to 51 respondents (ASN).

- 1) The results of the Multiple Linear Regression analysis show: $Y = 8.303 + 0.018X1 + 0.432X2 + 0.590X3$, meaning that:

- a) If the job analysis (X1) increases by 0.018 units, then the performance of ASN will increase by 0.018 units, and vice versa.
 - b) If recruitment (X2) increases by 0.432 units, then the performance of ASN will increase by 0.432 units, and vice versa.
 - c) If the selection of ASN (X3) increases by 0.590 units, then the performance of ASN will increase by 0.590 units, and vice versa.
- 2) Based on the ANOVA test or F test, it can be obtained an F-count of 11,411 with a significance level of 0.025. And the value of F-table = $F(k;n-k) = F(3;48) = 2.798$. Because the probability is smaller than 0.05 ($0.025 < 0.05$) and $F\text{-count} < F\text{-table}$ ($11.411 > 2.798$) it can be stated that the independent variables which include Position Analysis (X1), Recruitment (X2), and Employee Selection (X3) simultaneously or jointly affects the ASN Performance variable (Y).
- 3) Output SPSS Model Summary the amount of Adjusted R Square is 0.865. This means that only 86.50 percent of the variation in ASN performance (Y) can be explained by independent variables, namely job analysis (X1), recruitment (X2), and employee selection (X3). While the rest ($100\% - 86.50\% = 13.50\%$) is explained by other reasons outside the model that were not examined in this study.

Recommendation

1. Policy

- a. Position analysis (X1), Recruitment (X2), and Employee Selection (X3) have a positive influence on ASN Performance (Y), thus these three variables need to be maintained as a reference for ASN to move in to the Regional Secretariat.
- b. In order to improve the performance of ASN (Y) it is necessary to pay attention to the implementation of good Job Analysis (X1), Recruitment (X2), and Employee Selection (X3).
- c. The placement of ASN in the Regional Secretariat and even the regional government of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency as a whole should refer to the Position Analysis compiled by each SKPD which is summarized by the regional government through the Organizational Section.

2. Upcoming research

- a. There is a need for further research on the effect of job analysis, recruitment and selection of employees on ASN performance so that a broader picture or discourse can be obtained about job analysis, recruitment, employee selection and ASN performance.
- b. It is better to use independent variables that are different from the independent variables in this study.
- c. It is better to use more respondents, or the scope of the research is enlarged, from the scope of this research.

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